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Preventing Contamination Related to Global and Climate Change

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The presence of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) in soil, water, air and food is of concern and worry throughout society. Among the CECs, per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS, considered “forever chemicals”), and pharmaceuticals are referred to as the families of compounds that cause the most hazardous effects in the environment. These CECs are used intensively, and their disposal is not normally done correctly. Then, the detection of these different CECs has been consistently detected in alarming concentrations. High exposure levels to these compounds increase the risk of dangerous health issues for humans. Remediation techniques have been demonstrated not to be useful in reducing the presence of these compounds in the environment because they are limited or inefficient or are based on incineration emitting harmful air pollutants, such as fluorinated greenhouse gases (F-gases). These emissions contribute to those coming from refrigerants based on F-gases, by far the most relevant greenhouse gases from a climate perspective. Although F-gas emissions have been falling since 2015 and most of these refrigerants are currently being phased out, recycled pure F-gases are valuable because they can be reused in new-generation gas blends with much lower global warming potential. Since the recycling rates of F-gases in the EU are extremely low, the development of green technologies for the selective separation of these gases is vital to apply a circular economy and achieve the EU's goals for the climate.

This work is focused on the design (bio)materials to develop climate-friendly processes to separate PFAS and pharmaceuticals. The most appropriate (bio)materials will be custom-designed and evaluated for each specific application. The results are promising, opening a very interesting path to the optimization of a more sustainable process, which helps to solve one of the current environmental and health issues of great concern in Europe achieving a cleaner environment for the species and ensuring the well-being of species.